

Synthesis and Characterisation of High Surface Area Nano Silica for Li-Ion Battery Application from Rice Husk by Precipitation Method

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ABSTRACT

High-value applications such as the use of RHA in synthesis of silica, activated carbon, silica gels, porous carbon, zeolites, silicon carbide, silicon nitride, manufacturing of silicon chip and light weight construction materials insulations, catalysts, cordierite, ingredients for lithium-ion batteries, graphene, energy storage/capacitor, carbon capture. Other applications include in the manufacture. The rice husk contains 10-12 % silica. After the combustion one-fifth to one-quarter of the rice husk will change into ash Rice husks have been attracted as value added material towards waste utilization and cost. The white ash obtained from the combustion of this raw material at moderate temperature contains 92-97 % amorphous silica. RHA is an abundant agricultural by-product. It is rich in silica (about 60%) and can be made into economically viable raw material which can be used for production of silica gels and powders. The production of silica particles using RH needs to convert in ash and then using alkali and acid finally in Silica. Acid washing prior to extraction resulted in silica with a lower concentration of minerals. Synthesis done by precipitation using different acids namely, Sulphuric acid and nitric acid which yielded nano silica. Amount of silica duce for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. Amount of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for different for HCl are 5, 6, 6.40 and 7.81 gm resp. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for different for HCl are 41.66, 50, 53.3 and 65% resp. The maximum amount of silica contains 10-12 % so maximum yield considers as 12%. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for different for HCl are 41.66, 50, 53.3 and 65% resp. The maximum amount of silica contains 10-12 % so maximum yield considers as 12%.

Keywords – Rice Husk, Silica Gel, NaOH, Various Acids, % Yield.

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1. Introduction

Rice husks are the natural sheaths that form on rice grains their growth [1]. Removed during the refining of these husks have no commercial interest. Their major constituents are silica and cellulose which yields carbon when thermally decomposed under inert atmosphere. The rice husk contains about 50% cellulose, 25-30% lignin and 15-20% silica [2]. After the combustion one-fifth to one-quarter of the rice husk will change into ash Rice husks have been attracted as value added material towards waste utilization and cost. reduction in domestic and industrial processing [3]. Rice husk (RH) is widely available in rice producing countries like China and India which contributes 33% and 22% of global rice production respectively as by-product of the rice milling [4]. RH content ranges from 16-25% of paddy. High-value applications such as the use of RHA in synthesis of silica, activated carbon, silica gels, porous carbon, zeolites, silicon carbide, silicon nitride, manufacturing of silicon chip and light weight construction materials insulations, catalysts, cordierite, ingredients for lithium-ion batteries, graphene, energy storage/capacitor, carbon capture. Other applications include in the manufacture [5].

1.1. Silica Nanoparticle Production

Silica extracted from rice husk (5-10 g) dispersed in 500 mL of 0.5M NaOH aqueous solution and heated at 100 °C for 4 h under vigorous stirring to dissolve silica and produce sodium silicate. Solution obtained filtered to remove the nonreactive impurities [6]. Transparent filtrate of sodium silicate solution allowed to cool to room temperature and titrated with 10 % H₂SO₄ to pH 7 under vigorous stirring [7]. Sodium silicate has shown to be neutralized with diluted sulfuric acid to precipitate silica. Solution first stirred for 24 h and then aged for 48 h to allow silica gel to slowly precipitate. The formed gel fragmented, filtered and washed with water to remove the sulfate salt [8]. The clean silica gel was freeze-dried overnight to remove water. The SNPs product was stored in a vacuum desiccator for further characterization.

1.2 Silica Extraction from Rice Husks

Silica in rice husks were extracted during the pulping process of rice husks by the addition of NaOH solution due to its solubility in basic solution [9]. Rice husks were previously leached by 5% citric acid prior to pulping process in order to remove the inorganic impurities [10]. Extraction process carried out by adding 10 g rice husks in a beaker glass containing 500 ml NaOH 1 M. The mixtures heated until boiling for 2 hours in a hotplate while being stirred with

a magnetic stirrer at 600 rpm [11]. The beaker was covered by aluminum foil during heating to prevent the solvent loss due to evaporation. Silica was extracted from rice husk and form sodium silicate with NaOH solution [12]. The pulped rice husks were separated from the black liquor via filtration. The filtrate containing sodium silicate cooled down to room temperature prior to further treatment [13].

1.3 Silica Precipitation Using Acids

The black liquor containing sodium silicate was treated by acids for the rice husk bio silica recovery. Sodium silicate solution of about 200 ml was put in a beaker glass and slowly heated to 40 °C and mixed at 400 rpm with a magnetic stirrer [14]. The temperature held at 40 °C during the dropwise addition of acid solutions (HCl 3% or H₂SO₄ 3%) until pH 7 measured by pH-Meter CG 85. The temperature was continuously held at 40 °C while mixing for 90 minutes before cooling down to room temperature [15]. The bio silica would start to gel. The aging time set at 72 hours to allow the complete precipitation of bio silica [16].

1.4 Recovery of Rice Husk Bio Silica

The precipitated silica gel was filtered using a Buchner filter. Silica gel with brownish color was rinsed using a demineralized water for several times to get rid of the impurities such as salts containing sulphates [17]. The silica gel color getting transparent after rinsing. The silica gel dried in an oven at 150 °C for 24 hours to obtain bio silica. The dried bio silica milled and subjected to thermal treatment at 750 °C for 5 hours to remove the organic impurities of mainly lignin in the furnace. Bio silica powder was whiter in color after the thermal treatment [18]. The bio silica powder was cooled down to room temperature prior to further characterization. The mass of recovered bio silica powder weight [19].

1.5 Thermal Evaporation Method

The rice husks used obtained from rice mills. Further washed with tap water to remove soils and dirt and dried in the sun. The dried husks washed with distilled water and dried again in an oven at 60 °C. The dried husks chemically treated with 37 % HCL [20]. HCL diluted with distilled water to achieve a HCL solution with a 1% molar concentration. Substrates placed on the powder mixtures. Alumina boat and source materials placed in the middle of quartz tube furnace. Heated at 1250 °C in one atmosphere of nitrogen with a flow rate of 2L/min for 1 hour. Furnace cooled down to room temperature naturally [21].

1.6 Silica Applications

Silica can be used for silica aerogels to be used in super thermal insulators and dielectric materials. Raw material for the production of silicates and silica and in silicon chip in industry [22]. The uses of silica are in rubber industry as reinforcing agent, in cosmetics, in toothpastes as a cleansing agent and in the food industry as an anti-caking agent. For the preparation of inorganic materials like xylose, furfural, xylitol, ethanol, acetic acid and ligno sulfonic acid [23]. Amorphous silica of high purity, small particle size and high surface area can be of use as an adsorbent or catalyst support in fine chemical synthesis. Silica containing specimens by the thermal method and deposition from rice production waste which evaluated for their ability to remove different strains of microorganisms from the water. Removal efficiency of SiO₂ specimens and aluminum silicate sample prepared from rice husk to different strains of microorganisms higher than that of other specimens including commercial sorbent. Use of various processing schemes for rice production waste led to obtain efficient selective sorbents [24].

2. Literature Reviews

Silica extraction process carried out under controlled calcination conditions in an electric furnace at 600 °C. Hydrochloric acid treatment exhibited the highest performance among the other acid treatments. A purity of 95.55% amorphous silica with major impurities of K₂O, CaO and P₂O₅ indicating a relatively significant portion of it removed by acid treatment. This product then subjected to chemical precipitation followed by slow gelation to obtain SNPs. The BET specific surface area of 409 m²/gm, average particle size of 200±20 nm, spherical particle shape and purity of 97% indicate the successful production of silica nanoparticles. Silica extracted from rice husk (5 g) dispersed in 500 mL of 0.5M NaOH aqueous solution and heated at 100 °C for 4 h under vigorous stirring to dissolve silica and produce sodium silicate. The solution obtained filtered to remove the nonreactive impurities. The transparent filtrate of sodium silicate solution allowed to cool to room temperature and titrated with 10% H₂SO₄ to pH 7 under vigorous stirring [1]. Rice husk ash is treated with Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and Hydrochloric acid (HCl) to produce silica. The obtained silica is used for the various applications like automotive industry and cosmetic industry etc. The compound of silica like Sodium silicate (NaSiO₃) is used for water treatment, concrete treatment and cement production etc. [2]. Silica purity of the rice husk ash (RHA) calcined at 400, 450 and 500 °C 95.6%, 96.1 % and 95.89 % by weight respectively. The X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) pattern of

the silica obtained show that the silica amorphous with traces of crystalline phase. Amorphous nature of RHA and relatively high purity of silica content in it make it a suitable source of silica for zeolite synthesis [3]. Rice husk is a silica rich raw material comprising of about 90-98% silica. Rice husk has a large ash content and the presence of sodium silicate in its ash and rice husk becomes an economical source to extract silica from the rice husk ash which an extensive market and also helps in ash removal. Rice husk is a widely popular boiler fuel and the ash produced usually creates disposal issues. The silica extraction process offers a solution for waste clearance and recovers a valuable product together with certain useful associated applications. Silica gel's high specific surface area allows it to adsorb water readily and making it suitable as a desiccant (drying agent) in various purposes. Silica's inherent antifungal property makes it a potential antifungal agent [4]. Variation temperatures of 600, 700, 800, 900 °C at burning RH made different components SiO₂ and Si. Burning of RH with variation temperatures gives different components SiO₂ and Si. Burning RH variation temperatures 600, 700, 800, 900 °C represented highest SiO₂ and Si at 600 °C RHA with SiO₂ (44.4%) and Si (24.3%). [5]. The extracted Rice Husk Ash (RHA) samples at different temperatures and durations from locally available rice husk has been investigated and found that the extracted ash at the temperature of 800 °C for 2-hour duration is the optimum one in terms of amorphous silicon dioxide, with a percentage of SiO₂ at 91.74%. Thus, chemical and physical properties of the extracted ash at the temperature 800 °C for 2-hour duration fulfill the requirements of ASTM C618-03 standard as a pozzolanic material. Consequently, the developed ash can be used as a supplementary cementing material [12]. Rice husk is generally not recommended as cattle feed since its cellulose and other sugar contents are low. Furfural and rice bran oil are extracted from rice husk. Industries use rice husk as fuel in boilers and for power generation. Among the different types of biomasses used for gasification, rice husk has high ash varying from 18-20% [13]. Rice Husk Ash from different sources chemically treated and extracted amounts of Silica Gel were compared. It was found that Rice Husk Ash contains 70.90 percent to 84.50 percent Silica Gel [14]. Rice Husk which is considered as waste product from the Rice mills and sold at Rs. 300 per quintal can be used for production of value-added product such as silica which has its commercial sale value of Rs. 200 per Kg [15]. Rice husks burnt in agricultural fields in India because it is difficult to find other uses for them. Farmer's burn rice hulls usually under incomplete combustion conditions to avoid accidental fires. Amorphous silica prepared from rice husk ash by sol-gel method. Initially received from Rice husk ash

calcined at 400 °C, 500 °C, 600 °C and 700 °C for 5 hrs. to remove volatiles in the sample and determine the amorphous structure of SiO₂ [16]. The extraction result using variant of 15 to 60 minutes of heating time, rice husk ash produces silica gel with the highest silicone level at the 15-minute heating time, with the level at 24%. Other elements such as carbon and oxygen increase in its percentage according to the increase in heating intensity at extraction time [17]. By Rosario M. et al, RHA is obtained by burning of RH in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 500, 600 and 700 °C for 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 h. RHA treated with HCL and NaOH, amorphous silica produced at 700 °C for 3 h. [18]. High content of amorphous silica processed via washing, leaching with H₂SO₄ for 2 h then calcination for 2 h at 540 °C [19]. Amorphous and reactive silica form by treatment of RH using 0.1 N HCl acid and subjected to heat treatment at different temperatures from 500 to 1000 °C. RH with 1N HCL, 4.5 N H₂SO₄ and 1N HNO₃. Silica extraction carried under controlled calcination conditions in an electric furnace at 600 °C. A purity of 95 % amorphous silica [20].

3. Experimental Analysis

Raw Materials and Chemicals

1 N (HCl) Hydrochloric acid, (37%) 1 N HNO₃) Nitric acid, (90%) Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), (95%-98%) Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) were purchased from Research Laboratory Pune. Deionized Distilled Water was prepared in our laboratory. Rice Husk was made available from local field.

3.1 Extraction Process

Silica Extraction

The collected rice husks first washed with tap water to remove dirt and impurities and then dried in the oven at 60 °C for 24 h. Two methods of silica extraction examined including pretreatment by acid leaching and then combustion and combustion without any treatment. Three treatment solutions of 1N acid i.e., hydrochloric, nitric and sulfuric used for assessing leaching process performance. The combustion process conducted in an electric furnace at 600 °C for 6 h.

3.2 Silica Nanoparticle Production

Silica extracted from rice husk (5 g) dispersed in 500 mL of 1 N NaOH aqueous solution and heated at 100 °C for 4 h under vigorous stirring to dissolve silica and produce sodium silicate. The solution obtained filtered to remove the nonreactive impurities. The transparent filtrate of sodium silicate solution allowed to cool to room temperature and titrated with 1 N H₂SO₄ to pH 7 under vigorous stirring. Sodium silicate has shown to be neutralized with diluted sulfuric acid to precipitate silica. The solution first stirred for 24 h and then aged for 48 h to allow the silica gel to slowly precipitate. The formed gel fragmented, filtered and washed with water to remove the sulfate salt. The clean silica gel freeze-dried overnight to remove water.

3.3 Experimental Process

Rice Husk is sieved using 20-200 mesh size sieves. Rice husk obtained after sieving is washed with distilled water for cleaning purpose and sun dried for 48 hours. The rice husk obtained above is carbonized at 300 - 700 °C separately. Minimum time of duration of carbonization is 2 hours. Take 10 gm sample of ash which carbonized sample and Add 60 ml of 1 N NaOH and boiled in a covered 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks for 1 h with constant stirring. In above step is to dissolve the silica and produce a sodium silicate solution and then solutions filtered through Whatman No. 41 ash less filter paper and carbon residues washed with 100 ml of boiling water. The filtrates and washings allowed to cool to room temperature and titrated against 1N HCl with constant stirring to pH 7 for 2-3 hrs. After 18-20 hrs. the produced silica Deionized water (100 ml) added to gels and then the gels broken to make slurry. Slurries then centrifuged for 15 min at 2500 rpm clear supernatants discarded and the washing step repeated. Finally gel to be dried in oven for 3-4 hrs. to further analysis. The gels were transferred into a beaker and dried at 80 °C for 12 h to produce Xerogels. The above procedure repeated changing acid as 1N H₂SO₄ and 1N HNO₃ for maintaining pH. Find out the yield for different acids and also characterized the silica form.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Amount of Silica Produce for using HCl

Sr. No.	Conc. of NaOH	Amount of Silica Produce (gm)
01	1 N	5
02	2 N	6
03	2.5 N	6.40
04	3 N	7.81

Table % Yield of Silica using HCl

Table 1. shows Amount of silica produce for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. Amount of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for different for HCl are 5, 6, 6.40 and 7.81 gm resp.

4.2 Table: 1 % Yield of Silica for Various Concentration of NaOH using HCl

Sr. No.	Conc. of NaOH	% Yield of Silica using HCl
01	1 N	41.66
02	2 N	50
03	2.5 N	53.3
04	3 N	65

Table 1. shows % yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for different for HCl are 41.66, 50, 53.3 and 65% resp. The maximum amount of silica contains 10-12 % so maximum yield considers as 12%.

4.3 Graphical Representation for % Yield of Silica using HCl

Fig. no. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5

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Fig. 1. Graphical Representation for % Yield of Silica using HCl

5. Scope and Benefits

Merits

1. Production of silica from Rice Husk Ash which is abundantly available from rice mills.
2. Low temperature of processing hence energy conservation.
3. The silica thus produced has got high market value can be exported.
4. Solving unemployment problem.
5. The potential to earn foreign exchange by the entrepreneurs.

Demerits

The demerit of this process that it requires rigorous washing to get silica to the impurity associated with it.

6. Scope for Future Work

Effect of three parameters (acid treatment, temperature and heating rate) on the formation of black particles in rice husk silica ash studied. At low temperature (400 °C) the oxidation of carbon in the acid treated rice husk is sluggish. An industrial by product can be converted to a high value-added product by using a simple inexpensive method. A powder consisted of 92% of silica was prepared after calcinations of RHA at 700 °C for 5 hours. Silica from rice husk can be prepared under controlled temperature without any chemical's treatment, the bulk of investigation indicate that producing silica ash composites directly or into related silica filler composites, suggest that improvement can be achieved in the composite. Performance by modifying the physical and chemical nature of the filler. The extent of improvement, however, is greatly influenced by the ability to control the many relevant characteristics of the filler. The husks on leaching with acetic acid and oxalic acid of different concentrations followed by thermal treatment resulted in products with improve properties like purity, reactivity, brightness, surface area and pore volume. The leaching with mineral acids like HCl and HNO₃ of different concentrations followed by thermal treatment and measurement of properties showed that the acid treatment is almost equally effective in improving the silica properties.

7. Advantage of Using RHA

In advantage in using rice husk as raw materials for precipitated silica are superior and cost-effective compare to present technology of producing silica from quartz. Start from a raw material of little no cost and value which otherwise cause environmental pollution. Process is energy efficient and also consumes much lower energy compare to alternative process involving fusion of selected quality of sand.

8. Conclusion

The rice husk contains 10-12 % silica. After the combustion one-fifth to one-quarter of the rice husk will change into ash Rice husks have been attracted as value added material towards waste utilization and cost. The white ash obtained from the combustion of this raw material at moderate temperature contains 92-97 % amorphous silica. Amount of silica produce for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. Amount of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for different for HCl are 5, 6, 6.40 and 7.81 gm resp. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for HCl. % Yield of silica for various concentration of NaOH solution like 1, 2, 2.5 and 3 N solution for different for HCl are 41.66, 50, 53.3 and 65% resp. The

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